

Work Motivation And Professional Commitment Among Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract In the process of learning, the teacher plays the primary leadership role. Thus, in order to improve teacher effectiveness, it is necessary that educators understand the value of their work and have a strong work ethic. It is foreseeable in the modern era that a person cannot think about a quality of education without personal commitment. The purpose of the paper is to draw attention to the distinction (if any) between work motivation and professional commitment. 310 secondary school teachers who work in secondary schools affiliated to the U.P. Board were the subjects of the current study. The method employed was stratified random sampling. Both the professional commitment scale and the work motivation questionnaire were developed and validated by Kaur, Ranu, and Brar (2011) and K. G. Agarwal (2012), respectively, employed in the gathering of data. The results showed that, as compared to rural male and female teachers, urban male and urban female teachers have higher levels of professional commitment and work motivation.

Keywords Teacher Effectiveness, Work Motivation, Professional Commitment, Secondary School Teachers, Urban And Rural Teachers.

Introduction An educator ought to possess a through comprehension of the most recent pedagogical approaches and strategies. He should always be updating his knowledge, approach and methods. A teacher's personal and professional attributes support their professional competence. Better qualified and committed educators are essential in the classroom since even the best curriculum and syllabus are rendered useless by the passing of a devoted educator. As a result of highly qualified intellectuals opting not to become teachers in the current environment, educational quality has dramatically decreased. Consequently, it is a truth that certain aspects of education are to blame for the decline in educational quality. Schools need both professional commitment and motivation to fulfill their role as educational institutions that contribute to the achievement of national development goals.

Work motivation- work motivation is a collection of energy factors that come from both internal and external sources. The motivation at work determines the direction, intensity and form of work related conduct. It is a procedure used to motivate employees to do their tasks well. Workplace motivation can foster a positive attitude, promote teamwork and enhance teacher's performance. Teachers who possess a high degree of motivation tend to put in more effort and are able to overcome the ordinary workplace of obstacles with ease. This helps the school accomplish its goal and improves the learning environment in all aspects. A teacher's performance is impacted by a range of negative occurrences that are triggered by low motivation at work. Teachers who lack motivation may produce work of subpar quality, which can further hinder other educators' ability to accomplish their job well. Robbins (2005) describes work motivation as "the willingness to put in significant efforts towards organizational goals, contingent upon the effort's capacity to meet certain individual needs". Therefore, the psychological component of work motivation aids in teachers acquisition of job participation. Work motivation can be self motivated or provided by superiors to encourage subordinates to finish tasks quickly and effectively.

Professional Commitment: The profession is strongly linked to the work output, absenteeism, turnover and burnout of teachers. It also has a significant impact on the academic performance and attitude of students towards School. When someone says they are committed to a certain person, idea or course of action, they are expressing loyalty and a readiness to offer their all. A teacher's desire is to constantly improve and

hone his professional skills and knowledge in a variety of areas related to their line of work. The following six aspects of a teacher's duty or obligation can be used to gauge their level of commitment: A teacher's commitment to the learner, the institution, the workplace, achieving Excellence, society and human values. Professional commitment, according to Joffres and Haughey (2001), is defined as acting in a manner consistent with professionalism, making an effort to enhance one's practice, and dedicating time outside of school hours. In 2010 Frankenbery Taylor and Merseth define "Professional commitment as a work related attitude, that necessitates active engagement in the field. Additionally, they emphasised that it is helpful to distinguish between people who are not committed to their work and those who are. Teachers that are dedicated to their career collaborate with their students on classroom decisions so that they are part of the learning process. The aim is to foster positive work habits in their students and assist them in producing high quality work. In order to prepare their students for the future, professionally committed teachers place a strong emphasis on meeting their needs".

Need and significance:

There's a widespread belief these days that instructors don't have the required accountability for their work. The standard and nature of education are declining as a result of growing dissatisfaction among instructors regarding their work. This weak's quality improvement is the result of many factors. One of the factors contributing to the decline in quality is the teachers' lack of commitment and motivation. That may be the reasoning behind the National Council for Teacher Education's emphasis on the need to make the teacher commitment a fundamental component of teacher preparation (NCTE, 1998). Hence, it is crucial to acknowledge secondary school teachers' professional commitment and motivation for work. Therefore, this study is a modest attempt to learn more about secondary school teachers' job motivation and professional commitment.

Statement of the problem: Work motivation and professional commitment among secondary school teachers.

Objective of study Following are the objectives of the study-

1. To find out the difference between work motivation of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.
2. To find out the difference between work motivation of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.
3. To find out the difference between professional commitment of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.
4. To find out the difference between professional commitment of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.

Review of Literature

Reviews related to work motivation

Siddhpara and Parmar (2017) had worked on "Work motivation of employees in private sector". The outcome demonstrated that technical workers are more motivated to do their job than administrative workers. Employees with less than ten years of experience are more likely to be highly motivated at work than those with over ten years of experience.

Rajammal (2021) had "A study on work motivation of high school teachers in Chennai and Kancheepuram district". Results showed that a high degree of work motivation towards their profession was exhibited by the majority of the sample of high school teachers. Furthermore, the study found that there are notable difference in the work motivation of high school teachers based on factors such as school type, locality, and management style. According to their gender, age, year of experience and monthly pay, high school teachers are shown to have similar work motivation.

Rajni (2022) had worked on "Online teaching, self efficacy work motivation and professional commitment among secondary school teachers". The main conclusions showed that there is a strong connection between gender and location on the motivation for work.

Rashmi (2023) conducted a study on "Work motivation among high school and college teachers". According to the results, there is no discernible difference between college and high school teachers' level of work motivation.

Reviews related to professional commitment

Vasudev (2019) has worked on “Professional commitment among secondary school teachers in relation to their quality of work life and communication skills”. According to classificatory variables there is a weak but statistically significant correlation between professional commitment and the quality of one’s work life and its various dimensions.

Mahajan and Kauts (2022) conducted a “Study of professional commitment among secondary school teachers of Punjab with respect to type of schools”. Based on all elements of professional commitment, the study’s findings showed that secondary school teachers in private schools had a higher level of commitment than those in government schools.

Kanwar (2023) conducted research on “Professional commitment of school teachers in relation to their spiritual intelligence, emotional intelligence and school environment”. The findings suggested that there is a considerable positive correlation between all aspects of emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence and school environment and all aspects of professional commitment.

Sunitha and Kalaivani (2023) examined “Professional commitment of teachers in relation to their work motivation and self efficacy”. According to the study findings, female higher secondary teachers are more professional commitment to their male counterparts. There is a notable disparities in the level of professional commitment, regarding gender, school location, age, marital status, management style and teaching experience. Further, the work motivation of higher secondary school teachers is influenced by various factors such as age, gender, school location, marital status and amount of teaching experience. Regarding the form of management, there is no discernible variation in the work motivation of higher secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis Following are the hypothesis of the study-
 1. There exists no significant difference between work motivation of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.
 2. There exists no significant difference between work motivation of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.
 3. There exists no significant difference between professional commitment of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.
 4. There exists no significant difference between professional commitment of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.

Methodology Normative survey method has been used in the present investigation.
Target population: Teachers teaching in secondary schools of Meerut District formed the target population.

Sampling In this study sample of 310 secondary school teachers working in secondary schools affiliated to U.P. board was selected by using stratified random sampling technique.

Tools Used In the present study, the following tools were used.
 1. Work Motivation Questionnaire (WMQ- A) - Prepared and standardized by Agarwal (2012).
 2. Professional Commitment Scale- Prepared and standardized by Kaur, Ranu and Brar (2011).

Statistics Used in the Study **Statistical techniques used:** Following statistical techniques are used for the data analysis and interpretation. These are mean, standard deviation and t-test.
Procedure: Before the surveys were sent out, a rapport was first established with the subjects. Following that, they were given the proper instructions and given a work motivation questionnaire and professional commitment scale. After the task was finished, the questionnaires were gathered from the sample, and the data was statistically examined while taking the study’s objectives into account.

Analysis **Hypothesis 1** There exists no significant difference between work motivation of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.

Table 1: N, Mean, SD and t-value of rural male and urban male secondary school teachers on work motivation

	N	Mean	SD	SED	Df	t-value	Level of Significance
Rural Male	80	51.21	29.15	4.89	153	0.237	0.05
Urban Male	75	52.37	31.74				

It is obvious from table number 1 that calculated t-value 0.237 is less than table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance and df 153. Hence, the difference is not significant. Therefore, null hypothesis is being accepted. Hence, it may be concluded that urban male teachers have high work motivation (M=52.37, SD=31.74) in comparison to rural male teachers (M=51.21, SD=29.15).

Hypothesis 2 There exists no significant difference between work motivation of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.

Table 2: N, Mean, SD and t-value of rural female and urban female secondary school teachers on work motivation

	N	Mean	SD	SED	Df	t-value	Level of Significance
Rural Female	80	60.87	33.03	5.23	153	0.151	0.05
Urban Female	75	61.66	32.08				

It is clear from table number 2 that the calculated t-value is 0.151, which is less than table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance and df is 153. Hence the difference is not significant. Therefore, null hypothesis is being accepted. So, it may also be concluded that urban females have high work motivation (M= 61.66, SD=32.08) In comparison to rural female teachers (M=60.87, SD=33.03).

Hypothesis 3 There exists no significant difference between professional commitment of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers.

Table 3: N, Mean, SD and t-value of rural male and urban male secondary school teachers on professional commitment

	N	Mean	SD	SED	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Rural Male	80	86.23	45.17	7.40	153	0.110	0.05
Urban Male	75	87.05	47.04				

Above table number 3 indicate means (87.05, 86.23) and SD (47.04, 45.17) respectively. The t-value is 0.110 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, it can be said that null hypothesis 3 " there is no significant difference between professional commitment of urban male and rural male secondary school teachers" is not to be rejected. It is observed that rural and urban secondary school teachers do not differ significantly on professional commitment.

Hypothesis 4 There exists no significant difference between professional commitment of urban female and rural female secondary school teachers.

Table 4: N, Mean, SD and t-value of rural female and urban female secondary school teachers on professional commitment

	N	Mean	SD	SED	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Rural Female	80	123.17	45.79	6.19	153	0.286	0.05
Urban Female	75	124.94	28.90				

It is clear from table number 4 that the calculated t-value is 0.286, which is less than table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance and df is 153. Hence the difference is not significant. Therefore, null hypothesis is being accepted. So, it may also be concluded that urban females have high professional commitment (M= 124.94, SD=28.90) in comparison to rural female teachers (M=123.17,SD=45.79).

Findings

Following are the findings of the study-

1. Urban male teachers have high work motivation in comparison to rural male teachers.
2. Urban female teachers have high work motivation in comparison to rural female teachers.
3. Rural male teachers have low professional commitment in comparison to urban male teachers.
4. Urban female teachers have high professional commitment as compared to rural female teachers.

Conclusion

A vital resource for advancing high-quality education in the Indian educational system is the professional dedication of educators. All educational establishments ought to create an atmosphere that encourages instructors' motivation by giving them greater autonomy

in the participatory decision-making process. This will have a positive impact on their sense of loyalty to the company and to their line of work.

Suggestions for the future Study The following suggestions are offered which may stimulate prospective research work in this area.

1. The study could be extended to other district of UP.
2. A comparative study may be undertaken between different School systems such as CBSE, Navodaya schools, Kendriya Vidyalaya, etc.
3. Similar study may be carried out at various levels of education.

Limitation of the Study The present study have following delimitations. These are as follows-

1. The present study was delimited to secondary school teachers belong to schools affiliated with U.P. Board only.
2. The present study was delimited to in respect of sample size.
3. The present study was delimited to in respect of tools used.

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